

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIVERSITY OF SNAIL SPECIES (MOLLUSC: GASTROPODS) WITH GENETIC DIVERSITY USING MOLECULAR MARKER TECHNOLOGY

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In this article, my chosen field is Aquatic Animal Ecology. I plan to make the field of Animal Ecology my final project in the future. I think the specialty of Animal Ecology is that I can get to know more about the interactions of animals with their environment which can also affect human life, especially the Mollusk group. It's amazing for me to be able to know more about molluscs that some people hate mollusks. In addition, Aquatic Animal Ecology is a place for me to put my hope so that in the future I can give my best contribution to the advancement of scientific knowledge regarding Mollusks in my area, 96% of which are oceans. Because there is an endemic mollusk that is iconic in my city (Tanjungpinang) which is usually called the Gong-gong snail (*Laevisrombus canarium*). Then, in this assignment, I combined the field of Aquatic Animal Ecology with the field of Genetics. Because the field of Genetics has a broad study that can be combined with other fields in Biology. In addition, animal population density certainly has a relationship with genetic diversity. By combining the field of Aquatic Animal Ecology with Genetics, it is hoped that new research can be produced that provides many benefits for the community as well as continuing research.

Molluscs are a phylum of marine biota that have a high level of species diversity and similar morphological forms so that it often causes difficulties in identification (Appeltans et al., 2012). The nature of grouped gastropods is thought to be caused by several factors, including environmental conditions, substrate type, eating habits and methods of reproduction. In addition, the way of life of these grouped biota shows a strong tendency to compete with other biota, especially in terms of eating (Nurdin et al, 2016). Gastropods (snails) are one of the basic animal groups that play an important role in aquatic ecosystems, namely as primary consumers (herbivores) and secondary consumers (carnivores) (Campbell et al, 2004). Another important role of Gastropods is helping the process of mechanical decomposition of organic matter through their feeding activities (Fried and Hademenos. 1999). Some play a negative role because they are intermediate hosts of parasitic worms in humans (Djajasasmita, 1999). The abundance and distribution of gastropods in a waters is determined by the abiotic and biotic environment and the tolerance of gastropods to each of these environmental factors. Environmental factors have an important role for the life of living things in the process of their development including gastropods, therefore environmental factors are considered necessary to be measured (Zakaria et al, 2018). Influencing factors such as water chemistry, substrate type, food availability and biotic factors such as life cycle patterns, biotic relationships and the distribution of these gastropods (Suin, 2003). The spread of organisms is determined by their distribution pattern, this is influenced by the level of socialization of an organism in a population, the nature of the abiotic and biotic environments, interactions with other species, and the availability of resources (Hamidah, 2000). If the gastropod group has a high evenness index, it means that the ecosystem is a stressful environment (Yolanda et al, 2015).

The use of molecular markers has proved to be a useful tool for complex taxonomic identification where morphological characteristics are ambiguous or cryptic (Park et al., 2005). Random amplified polymorphic DNA-polymerase chain reaction (RAPD-PCR) technique is relatively simple and cheap method capable of differentiating taxa without the need to know their genomes as stated by (Williams et al., 1990). RAPD markers are dominant and result from the use of short (10 bases long) primers (synthetic oligonucleotides) of random sequence that can amplify multiple segments of genomic DNA by PCR. The number of segments depends on the number of sites of the genome recognized by a particular primer. The major reason for the success of RAPD analysis is the gain of a

large number of genetic markers that require small amounts of DNA without the need of a molecular characterization of the genome of the taxa under study (Altaf et al, 2017).

Molecular identification has become a method that can be used for precise and accurate species identification (Simbolon et al., 2021). One of the latest molecular marker methods used for species identification is mitochondrial DNA cytochrome oxidase I (mtCOI) (DNA barcoding) because it is non-recombinant and does not depend on environmental conditions (Palanisamy et al., 2020), so DNA barcoding has become the standard in molecular identification. b. DNA barcoding has been used to confirm the taxonomy of marine animals to the molecular phylogeny of Molluscs (Barco et al., 2016); this method also shows evidence of species diversity in molluscs in Pacific waters (Sun et al., 2016). Kress et al. (2015) showed that DNA barcoding could be an effective tool in the management and monitoring of marine biota. Meanwhile, phylogenetic is a taxonomic method that classifies species based on evolutionary history analysis which is carried out by analyzing both morphologically and DNA sequence analysis (Juniar et al., 2021). The use of DNA barcodes in molecular species identification in deep-sea shells has been carried out by Liu & Zhang (2018); the use of the COI gene combined with phylogenetic tree analysis and genetic distance is known to be able to identify and study the diversity and evolutionary history of deep-sea shells. All specimens can be identified well to the species level with a high level of species similarity, this confirms that the COI gene can be used to identify mollusc species well (Simbolon and Aji, 2021).

It can be concluded that the species diversity of snails (mollusks: gastropods) is closely related to genetic diversity. This study is very important because the gastropod group is a marine biota that can be used as an indicator to see the level of contamination of an environment. By knowing the diversity of this snail species we can manage and maintain it so that it is always awake. Find out the high and low diversity of gastropod species in an ecosystem, it can be done by looking at the genetic diversity. Molecular studies are needed in this identification. The method used is using molecular marker technology such as DNA barcode. By combining the study of animal ecology and genetics, it is hoped that it will provide clear and accurate results.

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